

BDAIM-2025

PROCEEDINGS

of the International Scientific and Practical Conference

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling
International Socio-Economic Processes

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

May 27, 2025

University of World Economy and Diplomacy
Moscow State Institute of International Relations
National University of Uzbekistan

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Big Data & AI for Global Socio-
Economic Modeling

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in Modeling

International Socio-Economic Processes

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(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – BDAIM-2025

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling International Socio-Economic Processes

The **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**, in collaboration with **MGIMO University** and the **National University of Uzbekistan (NUUz)**, hosted the international scientific and practical conference **BDAIM-2025** on **May 27, 2025** in **Tashkent, Uzbekistan**.

The main **goal** of the conference was to unite researchers, policy makers, experts, and educators to explore cutting-edge applications of **big data** and **artificial intelligence (AI)** in modeling **international socio-economic processes**. Particular emphasis was placed on interdisciplinary approaches and digital transformation in economics, governance, and education.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **Theoretical Foundations:** big data processing, machine learning algorithms, interpretability.
- **Socio-Economic Modeling:** global trade, finance, migration, and digital economies.
- **Global Challenges:** AI for climate change, pandemics, geopolitical risk management.
- **International Relations:** digital diplomacy, media analytics, conflict forecasting.
- **Ethics and Regulation:** AI governance, data protection, algorithmic responsibility.
- **Mathematical Models:** econometrics, game theory, uncertainty and risk analysis.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Credit Score Classification Using CNN-Based 2D Image Transformation and Machine Learning Integration

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In modern finance, credit scoring serves as a critical mechanism to evaluate the borrowing potential of individuals. Traditional models, such as logistic regression, often struggle to handle complex, heterogeneous datasets at scale. Deep learning approaches, particularly CNNs, have shown considerable promise in addressing these limitations [1]. This study introduces a novel hybrid strategy that integrates Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with classical machine learning algorithms. It utilizes ASCII-based 2D grayscale transformation of tabular financial data, facilitating the application of CNNs for deep feature learning.

A hybrid approach is used, combining CNN feature extraction with classical machine learning classifiers to produce accurate, scalable, and resource-efficient outcomes.

Historically, credit scoring has relied on statistical techniques like logistic regression and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) [2]. While effective for linear relationships, these models often underperform on complex datasets.

With the rise of deep learning, CNNs have gained attention for their ability to process image-based data. Recent advancements show potential in repurposing CNNs for tabular financial data, particularly by transforming such data into images for classification [3]. Similarly, by employing real world credit card data Zhang et al [4] accomplished credit card fraud detection models based on the CNN and machine learning algorithms, including Support Vector Machine (SVM) and random forest by achieving high accuracy results in both models.

This study utilizes the 'Credit Score Classification Clean Data' from Kaggle, comprising 31,695 records labeled as Good, Poor, or Standard (5). According to Pseudo-code of the grayscale technique, illustrated in Fig. 1 below each record is converted into a 14x14 grayscale image through ASCII encoding, facilitating CNN processing.

```

Algorithm 1: Pseudo-code of the grayscale technique
function convertToGrayscaleImage(data, width, height):
    grayscaleImage = initialize2DArray(height, width) #Create 2D matrix with 1D data array (data)
    for i from 0 to height-1: #Convert 1D data to 2D image
        for j from 0 to width-1:
            index = i * width + j #1D corresponding index in the array
            if index < length(data): #If the index is within the limits of the data
                grayscaleImage[i][j] = clamp(data[index], 0, 255) # Keep the value in the range 0-255
    return grayscaleImage
function clamp(value, min, max): #Function that keeps the value between 0 and 255.
    if value < min:
        return min
    else if value > max:
        return max
    else:
        return value

```

Figure 1. Pseudo-code of the grayscale technique

The process of conversion by Pseudo-code grayscale method was illustrated below in the Figure 2. In this study label "1" presents "good" class, label "2" represents "poor" class, and label "3" indicates "standard" class.

Figure 2. Transformation process of the data set as 2D Grey Scale image format

Six CNN models are trained, with DenseNet201 and ResNet18 yielding the most accurate results. Features extracted from a custom fully connected (NewFC) layer are

merged and refined using the ReliefF algorithm. These refined features are subsequently classified using KNN, LDA, Naive Bayes, and SVM to evaluate effectiveness. To employ CNN model, 70% of the data set was put in data set as a training set while 30 percent as a test set. The architecture of CNN model is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 3. Architecture of the 2D CNN model

After 1000 features were withdrawn from each CNN model they were classified. Then, each CNN model provides 1000 features in the previous layer, so called, fully connected layer, that means we obtain number of images in the dataset, a feature set with a matrix of [1000 x 31695], in other words [1000 x number of images].

Figure 4. Architecture of the 2D CNN model

As illustrated in Figure 3 we used hybrid model which amalgamates deep learning along with machine learning techniques to classify 2D credit score image dataset. While testing the data, in the Evaluation of Performance to observe multiple metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, precision, f-score, and accuracy level following five equations were computed.

$$Sensitivity (SE) = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positive + False\ Negative} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Specificity}(SP) = \frac{\text{True Negative}}{\text{True Negative} + \text{False Positive}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Precision}(Pre) = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}} \quad (3)$$

$$F - \text{score } (F - scr) = \frac{2 \times \text{True Positive}}{2 \times \text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive} + \text{False Negative}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Accuracy}(Acc) = \frac{\text{True Positive} + \text{True Negative}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{True Negative} + \text{False Positive} + \text{False Negative}}$$

Among the models tested, DenseNet201 outperformed with a classification accuracy of 99.47%, closely followed by ResNet18 at 99.00%. Post-processing using the Relief algorithm and traditional machine learning models further improved classification results, with most classifiers exceeding 99.9% accuracy. Fivefold cross-validation confirmed that the hybrid approach generalizes well across data splits and maintains high performance consistency.

The proposed CNN-ML integrated approach provides a highly effective solution for credit classification, leveraging image transformation to enable CNN processing of structured data. By combining deep feature learning with efficient traditional classification techniques, the model demonstrates superior scalability and precision. This work presents a viable framework for deployment in real-time credit assessment systems and encourages further research into hybrid architectures for financial analytics.

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